

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Evaluation Report (triage round 2) for **TEBT-2024-0006**

Submission information table

Submission Title	Assessing the Effects of a Precommitment Policy Applied During Peer Review
Submission Reference	TEBT_2024-0006
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin ORCID: 0000-0003-2724-7882
Number of Reviewers	2
Submission Type	Research Letter
Preprint DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11122252
Evaluation Type	Acceptance Note :: Round 1
Evaluation Date	28 July 2024
Recommendation	Accept
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	The first version of this research letter was well received overall. Reviewers had a few suggestions for improvements that well successfully addressed by the authors in the resubmitted version.

Summary of article and editor recommendations

This research letter gives an overview of the planned methods for a meta-experiment (a planned meta-analysis of individual journal-based experiments) to test the impacts of the implementation of a Registered Revisions policy. Registered Revisions is a new pre-commitment policy triggered during peer review following acceptance of a Revision Plan.

Acceptance note for inclusion in final evaluation report

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor after 1 round of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 1 round of peer-review.

During triage, the handling editor did not identify any issue with the initial submission and the manuscript was advanced to peer-review.

During peer-review, the evaluators recommended that authors expand on the context for editorial innovations across disciplines as well as provide some more detailed descriptions of some of elements of the experimental approach. The authors addressed these issues by providing the required context and clarifications, as well as a workflow template.

Again, the peer review process stresses the need to investigate innovations across disciplines. Further, as ever, a picture is worth a thousand words, and here a complex process is best illustrated visually.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at [10.5281/zenodo.11191604](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11191604).